

AFFIRMATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION THROUGH TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

According to University Education Commission “Education is a great instrument of social emancipation by which a democracy establishes maintains and protects the spirit of equality among its members.”

This paper deals with Assurance of Total Quality Management (TQM) in higher education in India. Education is an important instrument of social, economic, scientific and technological development of any country. It is an important source of social and economic development of the country. Education is an important tool of all round development of personality, through which the people can achieve the great success in their life. The constructive and qualitative development of the nation and its people depends upon quality of education. Therefore, today total quality management in higher education is urgently needed for effective and qualitative development of the people. The effective and qualitative development of the nation totally depends upon the total quality in higher education. The quality education plays a very significant role in effective and qualitative development of the people. The all-round development of the people can only be possible through total quality management in higher education. Therefore, today, there is an urgent need of assurance of total quality management for qualitative improvement in higher education.

***Key Words:-** Introduction, role of higher education in national development, concept of management, concept of T.Q.M., assurance of T.Q.M in higher education, problems in quality of management in higher education, dimensions of improvement of TQM in higher education, role of NAAC in management of T.Q.M., role of technology in T.Q.M., conclusion.*

Introduction:

Education is an important instrument of mental, social, and economic development of

the individuals. True education must make the individual free and easy instead of making sophisticated and complex. Education is the light of life which can bring about the concept of self-rule and sovereign democracy in the lives of people. It conveys different meaning for different regions under different spheres.

Education is concerned with the development of the whole nation through the education and training of future citizens and development of their personality. Hence, educational administration should be more efficient and liberal than civil administration. Any slackness or carelessness in the programmes of the development of the personality of children will affect the development programmes of the whole nation and cause a great loss to the nation. Hence, educational programmes should be changed accordingly to the need of time.

According to Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru expressed his view as: ‘A university stands for humanism, for tolerance, for reason, for adventure of ideas and for the search of the truth. It stands for the onward march of the human race towards even higher objectives. If the Universities discharge their duties adequately, then it is well with the nation and the people.’

Role of Higher Education in National Development:

Higher education plays an important role in developing the nation to a great extent. It helps the members of the society to get live, to develop well and to improve the strength of the nation. It inculcates to reform the conduct and behaviors and integrity of personality in the individuals. There is pursuit of truth and excellence in man and only the higher education can direct the path of it. On the whole, since the past, higher education has been playing its due role in developing the nation to a greater extent thought not to the extent desired.

The benefits of higher education accrue primarily to the recipient, and by implication, that the benefit to the nation is not much, suggests a lack of appreciation of the role of higher education in national development. In fact, there is appreciation of the fact that higher education provides the competencies that are required in different spheres of human activity ranging from administration of agriculture, business, industry, health, communication and extending the arts and culture. In fact, the World Bank document itself states: ‘Higher education is of paramount importance for economic and social development. Institutions for higher education have the main responsibility for equipping individuals with the advanced knowledge and skills required for positions of responsibility in government, business and the professions.’

As mentioned earlier the National Policy on Education, 1986, visualizes education to be process of empowerment through the development of knowledge, skills and values.

The higher education system of a country plays a significant role in the creation of skilled human resources. In the emerging scenario of knowledge based society across the globe, India is well placed with potential brains needed for the revolutionary changes.

The education system should develop necessary infrastructure for the evolution of “**Knowledge Society**.” It is also aimed at imparting quality to the teaching-learning process and develops a purposeful “**Research Culture**” in India. In the emerging scenario of the knowledge-based society across the globe, India is well placed with potential brains needed for the revolutionary changes.

Concept of Management:

According to Morell (1969), management is that activity in an organization which consists in deciding upon the ends (goals) of an organization and the means by which the goals are to be effectively reached. Thus, management in education means to decide the goals of an educational institution and the activities to be conducted to achieve these goals

According to Terry (1971), also holds a similar view about the concept of management, management is a distinct process consisting of planning, organizing, actualizing, determining and accomplishing stated objectives by the use of human beings and other resources.

Management of education is a cooperative human endeavor. Although the head of the institution is the manager of this human enterprise, yet the cooperation of teachers, parents, students and the community members is essential for effectively managing the institution. Even if advanced technologies like the computers are now increasingly used in the management process, yet it is the human element which lies behind all effective managements. The scope of management of education is very vast. It includes all aspects and all levels of education. Management has five aspects such as planning, organizing, directing, motivating, co-ordination and evaluation etc.

Concept of Total Quality Management (TQM):

As far as total quality management (TQM) in higher education is concerned, it refers to the process of ensuring highest quality on a sustained basis throughout an organization through the involvement people working for the organization. Thus, it is not a narrow concept of the

quality of a product or service, but a broad concept covering the whole organization. Of course, in all this the customer is the focus. The total quality management is concerned with customer's satisfaction. In the field of higher education the student becomes the focus.

The quality concept was initially focused on tangible products manufactured by industrial organizations. Later it spread to cover service like utilities involving municipal services, police, health and education. Thus, the quality concept evolved from manufacturing to service, from product to organization; and from physical inspection to quality management. In the prevailing environment of globalization and free market TQM has become the most sought after and essential pre-requisite for the success of any business dealing with any product or service.

Management of Total Quality in Higher Education:

Total quality management in case of services like higher education has a number of distinct features. A basic feature is the difficulty in measurement. While quality in higher education is reflected in the evaluation of students' attainments, it is very difficult to measure the contribution of the various factors for the rise in quality. Another feature is that quality in teaching is also influenced by the response of the student. Further, in the provision of services the role of personnel providing the service is very important and can influence quality to a significant extent. In fact, quality may vary at different times and different circumstances. Thus, total quality management in a service like education presents a challenge to the educationists.

However, pursuit of Total Quality Management in higher education is very essential if the quality of human resources is to be raised, otherwise success in the prevailing era of information technology and globalization will remain a distant dream.

Assurance of Total Quality in Higher Education:

Quality assurance is one of the central issues in higher debates today. The serious problems include assuring the quality of adverse academics of teaching, admission, and Infrastructure. Quality assurance in the private sector is especially important. Many countries are moving towards instituting more careful quality assurance and regulations of degree offerings. Although national mechanisms are necessarily at the heart of a system of ensuring

quality higher education, relevant International assurance is also a must.

Higher education institutions are promoted with the objectives of developing ideal citizens who are clear about their roles and responsibilities in the society and in spreading awareness about the importance of being educated. In this sense, these institutes have a role to play in promoting universalization of education. (University News, vol.44 (01) January 2006, page 5, 9) Accessibility and quality improvement are inseparable dimensions of higher education. Over emphasis on one at the cost of another would be counterproductive.

While ensuring the provision for necessary and inevitable qualitative expansion of higher education, it is equally important to improve the quality of higher education. If we fail on this front, institutions of higher learning would find it difficult to meet the challenges of globalization of higher education. Emphasis on quality parameters become all the more necessary in the light of mushrooming growth of private institutions with the opening of the economy. (University News, 43 (41), October 10.16.2005)

The advent of globalization in the area of education as in other services called, for the internationalization of Higher Education in India. The important concept implies the acceptance of a World Wide Quality Label (WWQL) of quality assurance in higher education. A system of education is expected to be responsible and to meet the needs of students. One of the activities of Global Alliance of Traditional Education (GATE) is to establish principles and policies for evaluating quality of education.

Problems of Quality Management in Higher Education:

After independence, lots of progress and development has been done in higher education in India. In spite of this, there are still some main problems in higher education due to poor educational planning, poor educational administration, poor educational management and poor control and supervision and lack of total quality management etc. These are the main obstacles which create problems in maintaining the total quality management in higher education. The main problems of higher education at present in India are as follow:

Problems in Higher Education:

1. Aimless education system
2. Defective and unsuitable curriculum
3. Lack of qualified Teachers and Professionals
4. Low standard and defective teaching

5. Lack of knowledge of teaching methodologies
6. Lack of proper infrastructure
7. Lack of proper physical facilities
8. Lack of specialized education
9. Lack of job-oriented courses-technical and professional
10. Problem of medium of instruction
11. Defective examination system
12. Defective evaluation Process
13. Poor working conditions
14. Problems of proper Management
15. Lack of guidance and counselling centers
16. Lack of proper leadership in educational administration
17. Wide gulf between the teachers and students
18. Political interference
19. Indiscipline problems
20. Wastage of resources

Due to these existing main problems in higher education, it is very difficult to maintain the total quality management in higher education at present in India. First of all, we have to solve these main problems of higher education then after the total quality management can be maintained in higher education.

India is a great democratic country in the world its 70% population live the out of cities. There is a crisis of higher education in rural areas. The students rush to cities for getting higher education. There is a hardly found any institution of higher education in the rural areas due to poor management of higher education.

Dimensions of Improvement of Total Quality Management in Higher Education:

To maintain the total quality assurance in higher education, the higher institutions and universities should follow the standard of higher education in admission procedures to take the quality intake of students; appropriate pedagogy, proper placement, quality faculty development and quality infrastructure in higher education etc. There are following important dimensions of maintaining the total quality management in higher education such as:

Dimensions of Improvement of Quality Management in Higher Education:

1. Quality in students' admission procedures
2. Quality in pedagogy-teaching methodologies
3. Quality in placement of students
4. Quality in selection of faculty
5. Quality in infrastructure
6. Quality in examination process
7. Quality in evaluation process
8. Quality in educational management and control
9. Quality in administrative process
10. Quality in teachers' salary and promotions
11. Quality in teachers' orientation and refresher programmes
12. Quality in teachers' welfare programmes
13. Quality in teachers' academic programmes
14. Quality in teachers' academic facilities
15. Quality in teachers' academic development

Thus, the total quality management in higher education can be done by implementing the above mentioned dimensions. Therefore, we should follow these dimensions to maintain the total quality management in higher education.

The vital need for every institution of higher education to go in for Total Quality Management. However, it is necessary to follow a systematic procedure, avoid pitfalls and take adequate precautions to achieve sustained progress.

The systematic procedure should involve the following points to maintain the total quality management in higher education such as:

- (a) Securing top management commitment
- (b) Formation team
- (c) Formation team
- (d) Developing a clear policy statement
- (e) Framing specific objectives/guidelines/procedures
- (f) Preparing a detailed plan of action
- (g) Effective implementation

It is necessary to ensure that participation of all concerned, to make the whole process interesting to monitor periodically and keep the development sustained necessary in the light

of mushrooming growth of private institutions with the opening of the economy.(University News, 43(41), October 10.16.2005).

Role of NAAC in Management of Total Quality in Higher Education:

The UGC established the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) in 1994 as an apex body to promote and focus on the quality consciousness among the institutions of higher learning and to ensure quality assurance. It set up the internal NAAC Committee and involves the faculty in the preparation of the 'self evaluation' as required by the NAAC which was highly revealing.

Total quality management practices include continuous curriculum development, students' counselling, support to faculty to update skills, support to administrative staff and link with business and industry.

The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) is playing a vital role in enhancement and maintaining the quality assurance in the higher education. It evaluates and directs the higher educational institutions and universities for qualitative development and quality improvement in the areas of admission procedures, teaching methodologies, examination system, evaluation process, selection of faculty and infrastructure etc. The NAAC plays an important role in maintaining the of overall total quality in higher education.

Role of Technology in Quality Management of Higher Education:

The quality of higher education can be improved considerably through extensive and optional use of audio-visual technologies, computers and internet networks etc. The courses should be so designed that the use of these technologies is made an integral part of the teaching programmes and classroom activities and to be a supplement in strengthening the learning facilities for students. Recent emphasis of higher education has been mostly on manpower development and mainly focus on skilled manpower development.

“Quality of higher education can also be improved by inducting quality-oriented objectivity in merit promotions under the career advancement schemes. Specialization of weightage for teaching, research publication and research supervision would help in making the schemes more transparent and credible.”

The prerequisite to plan for a better future is an understanding of the changes and their impact on the system of higher education its quality assurance, which is the emerging trend in higher education. (University News October: 2005-volume 43(41).

the progress sustained.

Conclusion:

As John Dewey stated, “a socially efficient individual should be able to control his environment and fulfill his possibilities. All education proceeds by the participation of individuals in the social consciousness of the race”.

Higher education, ultimately is to be directed to the intellectual maturity and flowering of the soul. It is the duty of all sections of society to protect and promote education as the fundamental human right.

In the prevailing environment of globalization and free competition, higher education will become an international service with high competition. Only a sustained movement towards Total Quality Management can enable any institution concerned with higher education to stay in business and achieve success. Shaking off academic inertia and a change in mind-set are essential prerequisites. Of course, success in Total Quality Management will be highly rewarding for all-students, teachers, institutions of higher education and the society in general.

Therefore, today there is a need of assurance of total quality management and total quality improvement in higher education to face the present challenges in India and world-wide. So there is an urgent need of drastic changes in educational planning, educational administration and educational management and supervision, teaching-pedagogy, admission procedures of the students and selection procedure of the faculty members to maintain the total quality management in higher education.

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